

Teachers' Intervention Strategies *vis a vis* Students' Performance in English

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Abstract:- The Department of Education has ensured the continuity of learning even amid the Covid 19 pandemic. In Light of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency, the Philippine Department of Education has ascertained that learning outcomes still be obtained successfully through the provision of continuous upskilling of teachers, adoption of various learning delivery modalities, streamlining of the curriculum, institution of the Most Essential Learning Competencies, practicing sustained intervention strategies for learners at-risk, maintaining close partnerships with internal and external stakeholders and many more. These steps taken by the Department are determined steps to ensure that no student is left behind.

The study utilized a basic research design observing document analysis method which basically aimed to analyze documentary evidence utilizing a systematic procedure. Data were gathered from the Learning Outcomes Assessment Report submitted by all municipalities and inter-coding through Focus Group Discussions (FGD) was done to validate the findings.

It was found that employing intervention strategies is crucial in achieving proficiency in the English subject. The different schools in the Division employed six common and frequently used strategies namely the provision of adequate time to accomplish the activities/tasks/outputs; sustaining constant communication to parents, home learning facilitators or guardians; provision of supplementary activities and worksheets that are MELC-aligned and needs-based, modification of tasks based on students' academic performance and comprehension level; preparation of additional ICT-based instructional materials like slides presentations, videos, and audio materials; and closely monitoring of students' progress through continuous online and offline follow-ups including home visitations. These are aligned with those strategies being employed by educators worldwide as a unified response to the Covid19 pandemic.

Keywords:- *Intervention, Intervention Strategies, Learning Outcomes*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education has ensured the continuity of learning even amid the Covid 19 pandemic. In fact, with the implementation of DepEd Order No. 012 s. 2020 or the

Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) for School Year 2020-2021 in Light of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency, the Department has ascertained that learning outcomes still be obtained successfully through the provision of continuous upskilling of teachers, adoption of various learning delivery modalities, streamlining of the curriculum, institution of the MELCs or the Most Essential Learning Competencies, practicing sustained intervention strategies for learners at-risk, maintaining close partnerships with internal and external stakeholders and many more. These steps taken by the Department are determined steps to ensure that no student is left behind.

Thus, the assessment of learning outcomes by the end of the challenging academic year 2020-2021 is deemed vital. This is to measure students' rate of success despite the many challenges that the educative process encountered because of the health crisis. The students were still given the examinations in the form of summative tests, assignments, quizzes, attendance, performance tasks and other graded points related to the course. Garcia and Al-Safadi (2014) define these as components of their academic performance. This academic performance impacts the attainment of the desired learning goals, or the most essential learning competencies, of various subjects across the curriculum. Pursuant to DepEd Order. 73, s. 2012, or the Guidelines on the Assessment and Rating of Learning Outcomes under the Kto12 Basic Education Curriculum, the measurement of learning or the students' academic success will still be based on how well they accomplished the content and performance standards as stipulated in the course/subject

As stated in the study made by Barrot (2018), as per the Department of Education (2016), the English curriculum in the Philippines has four components: language learning process, effective language use, making meaning through language, and holistic assessment. These components, into which the MELCs are aligned, had been the basis of many a teacher strategy to minimize the number of students who fall behind the academic progression in English. Teachers at the microlevel endeavored to implement different strategies to lessen the disparity between what students are expected to learn versus they have actually learned in class.

In this study therefore, the researchers will endeavor to determine what are those strategies used by the English teachers from grades 7-10 to address learning gaps during the school year 2020-2021 in the Division of Cavite Province. It will try to identify what those strategies are and how successful were they in enhancing the performance of students

in the English subject. Further, the study will also seek to find out the intervention activities that satisfy the needs of the target learners. By thematically coding these intervention strategies and activities used by teachers in the field based on the four components of the Philippine curriculum in English, the researchers hope that a viable list of intervention strategies be recommended for teachers in the Division.

II. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study endeavors to evaluate the effectiveness of the different strategies employed by the Junior High School English teachers in their classes during the school year 2020-2021 in the Division of Cavite Province.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the different strategies utilized by the teachers in addressing learning gaps based on Learning Outcomes Assessment results of the fourth quarter in SY 2020-2021?
2. What is the success rate of these intervention strategies on the academic performance of student in the English subject?
3. What are the common characteristics of the intervention activities employed in the field?

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Intervention strategies mean a plan for staff action that outlines methods, techniques, cues, programs, or tasks that enable the child to successfully complete a specific goal ([https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/intervention strategies](https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/intervention-strategies)). With effective intervention strategies in place, target learners may be able to achieve considerable academic progress, increased attainment of learning goals, and ultimately improve learning outcomes (<https://afaeducation.org/>)

In a study conducted by Tudor, Baker, Gersten, Baker and Smith (2015) on the effectiveness of reading intervention for English learners, they were able to review various experimental studies published from 2000 to 2012 that assessed the effects of harnessing intervention strategies for learners with at-risk or those experiencing learning difficulties. With a set criterion for choosing the published scholarly articles, the study showed that the intervention strategies used to address skills like beginning reading skills and reading or listening comprehension skills had significant moderate-to-large effects on learners. They pointed that the interventions in the studies include explicit instruction and that some used published intervention programs. Variables like group size, time or length of intervention, and type of personnel delivering the intervention were not significant predictors of outcomes.

Due to restricted physical interactions and the imposed community quarantines in various localities, teachers have also utilized various online platforms in the delivery of not just learning content but also learning interventions.

Based on a study conducted by Safapour, Kermanshachi, and Taneja (2019), most students taught using the traditional teaching methods that rely solely on the use of textbooks do not reach the expected maximum level of learning absorption. With the introduction of nontraditional teaching methods such as flipped classroom, gamification, case study, self-learning, and social media, learner achievement has been optimized because they (the nontraditional teaching methods) may be tailored to suit learners' abilities most effectively. They researchers focused on addressing questions regarding identifying the benefits of the said teaching methods and categorizing them. Their analysis resulted in practical guidelines in using the five nontraditional teaching methods incorporating the most effective teaching styles with the course objectives and the learners' abilities as bases.

It is also important to note that Barrot (2018) conducted a study about the reforms in the English curriculum in the Philippines, looking into the issues and challenges met from the 21st century standpoint. The research sought to examine the Kto12 English curriculum by looking into the Language Arts and Multiliteracies Curriculum and how it is aligned or consistent with the 21st century principles in language teaching and learning. The findings of the study show that the curriculum needs to improve its specificity, coherence, and integration with some important principles in 21st century learning and language teaching and learning.

There have been many studies conducted on how teachers address learning deficiencies, or the kinds of intervention strategies utilized by teachers in the classroom to achieve specific goals, but none so far were conducted on identifying specific intervention strategies used by teachers in English classes based on the learning outcomes assessments.

IV. SCOPE AND LIMITATION

This study focused on examining the different intervention strategies of English teachers at the different public secondary schools in the Division of Cavite in relation to the performance of students in the subject. It venture to identify what intervention strategies were employed to address learning gaps in the attainment of the most essential learning competencies, the success rate of these intervention strategies based on the performance of students in the English subject, the activities that satisfy the need/s of the target learners, and the common characteristics of intervention activities that contribute to the success or failure of the learners' performance which can be bases for recommendation of the best strategies/activities to be used by the teachers. Furthermore, using the four components of the 2016 Philippine curriculum in English namely language learning process, effective language use, making meaning through language, and holistic assessment, the various intervention strategies and activities used by teachers in their English classes were coded.

This study based its analysis heavily on the information submitted to the Schools Division Office – Cavite Province on learning outcomes assessment.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Sampling

Documents were the main source of data for this study. Thus, the study utilized convenience sampling where in the researchers used and review all available documents to attain the goal and objective of this study. Furthermore, English Teachers and Junior High School Students in the Division of Cavite Province also served as the respondents of this study because the data reflected on the Learning Outcomes Assessment results came from them.

B. Data Collection

A permission letter was formally sent to the proper authorities before the conduct of the study, the same letter also includes the request asking for access to the various documents needed. Upon approval, the researchers retrieved these documents and treated them with the utmost confidentiality.

The Document Analysis method was used to gather both the qualitative and quantitative aspects of the documents. The qualitative data from the documents were coded by the

researchers to generate the emerging themes. Furthermore, all the quantitative data were treated using the appropriate statistical tool.

VI. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

During the fourth quarter of the School Year 2020-2021, the eighteen (18) municipalities in the division of Cavite Province submitted the Learning Outcome Assessment Report. This report contains the mean, standard deviation (SD), and mean percentage scores (MPS) in tabular form. Additionally, this report also includes the various intervention strategies utilized by the teachers from the different schools in the Division to address the least mastered competencies in English.

With this data, the researchers were able to determine the common and frequently used strategies utilized by the teachers in addressing learning gaps based on the Learning Outcomes Assessment results of the fourth quarter in S.Y. 2020-2021.

Table 1 The Different Intervention Strategies Used

Intervention Strategies	Frequency per School	Percentage of use
1. Provided more adequate time to accomplish the activities/tasks/outputs	14	20.59
2. Sustained constant communication with parents, home learning facilitators, or guardians	10	14.71
3. Provided supplementary activities and worksheets that are MELC-aligned and need-based	13	19.12
4. Modified tasks based on students' academic performance/comprehension level	10	14.71
5. Prepared additional ICT-based instructional materials (slides presentation, videos, audio)	8	11.75
6. Monitored students' progress closely through continuous online and off line follow-ups including home visitations.	13	19.12
TOTAL	68	100

Based on the table, results show that the intervention strategies utilized by the schools may be categorized into six. The most common and frequently used strategy is the provision of more adequate time to accomplish the activities/tasks/outputs with a frequency of 14. Next is Provision of supplementary activities and worksheets that are MELC-aligned and need-based, followed by monitoring students' progress closely through continuous online and offline follow-ups including home visitations with both strategies having a frequency of 13. Then, strategies on sustaining constant communication with parents, home learning facilitators, or guardians and modifying tasks based on students' academic performance/comprehension level follow with a similar of frequency of 10. The least common strategy is the preparation of additional ICT-based

instructional materials (slides presentation, videos, audio) with a frequency of 8.

These intervention strategies were the ones employed by the teachers because of the new normal setup. Taking into consideration the modular and online learning delivery modality adopted by the schools, the teachers deemed it best to adjust the time to allow the learners in accomplishing and submitting their outputs. They also provided modified supplementary activities and worksheets and adjusted their level depending on the capacity of the students in order for them to cope with the demands of the subject. Some schools indicated the use of various ICT-based instructional materials. Since there is no physical or face-to-face interaction, the teachers displayed resourcefulness in reaching out and communicating with students and parents.

They used text messaging, facebook chat, audio or video calls, and other platforms to deliver instructions, guidelines, and reminders. Some teachers even executed home visitation amidst the pandemic to encourage parents and students to continue schooling and pursue scholastic goals.

Table 2 The Mean Percentage Scores (MPS) and Standard Deviation (SD) of 18 Municipalities

DISTRICT	MPS	SD
Alfonso	75.00	9.61
Amadeo	82.00	6.37
Carmona	76.00	7.66
General Emilio Aguinaldo	84.00	5.05
General Mariano Alvarez	78.00	8.89
Indang	76.00	7.49
Kawit	79.00	8.10
Magallanes	72.00	7.48
Maragondon	80.00	6.30
Mendez	76.00	8.06
Naic	78.00	5.85
Novelita	75.00	6.54
Rosario	77.00	8.91
Silang	76.00	8.85
Tagaytay City	83.00	6.48
Tanza	79.00	7.18
Ternate	78.00	6.50
Trece Martirez City	79.00	6.67
AVERAGE	77.94	7.33

Table 2 shows the Mean Percentage Scores (MPS) and Standard Deviation (SD) obtained during the fourth quarter of S.Y. 2020-2021 by the eighteen municipalities in the division of Cavite Province.

The results show that the average mean percentage score is 77.94. Based on the DepEd Memorandum No. 160 series of 2012 or the Maximizing of the National Achievement Test (NAT) Results to Raise the Achievement Levels in Low Performing Schools, this MPS of 77.94 is equivalent to Moving Towards Mastery (MTM) because it falls within the range of 66-85.

Looking at this figure vis-à-vis the DO 160, s. 2012, it qualifies the standard passing rate, meaning, the MPS indicates a satisfactory ratio between the number of correctly answered items and the total number of test questions. These results point to the success of the intervention strategies employed by the teachers. The different schools even seconded this finding stating the success of using these strategies in the Learning Outcome Assessment Report. This MPS does not qualify the schools in the Division of Cavite Province either as High Performing or Low Performing schools.

Fig 1 Alignment of the Strategies Used to the Research-based Strategies by Alexander (2021)

The diagram shows the alignment of the strategies employed by the teachers of DepEd Cavite Province to the research-based strategies employed by the administrators to support efforts to improve student outcomes, accelerate learning, and help address interrupting schooling as forwarded by Alexander (2021). Evidently, the intervention strategies of DepEd Cavite are congruent to the steps that need to be taken to ensure that no student is left behind despite the global health crisis. These initiatives include the use of digital technology, personalized approach, involving family and parental support, and giving consideration to the mental and social well-being of learners.

VII. DISSEMINATION AND ADVOCACY PLAN

For dissemination, the results of the study will be used as a basis for the intervention strategies that the teacher will use inside the classroom for the succeeding school years to more effectively address the learning needs of the students in the English subject. Further, this study will be an instrument in providing the best teacher intervention program giving due consideration to the current condition of the locality where the school from or located. In addition, the plan for dissemination will point out the best practices of different schools in the division to be adopted in order to improve the learning outcomes and become one of the High Performing schools in the country.

For advocacy, this research will target to continuously achieve the Department of Education’s mission and vision in promoting quality learning amidst global pandemic. Also, this research will aim to improve both the teachers’ and students’ technological awareness and competence in the field of education.

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